

LAND POTENTIAL 2015

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Abstract:

In this paper authors has researched utilization of land potentials in the world, Europe, Serbia and its ratio according to population. On the results of research authors remark that relation toward very important resources are not satisfied at the global and national level. Permanent grow worlds population from one side and limited land from other side must be very seriously warning for the creators of the national governments and wider union of states that responsibility relation in utilization of this resource.

Key words: land, population, non rational utilization

1. INTRODUCTION

On the Earth, water (oceans, seas, lakes and rivers) and land (agriculture and others) are in relation 6:4. This relation has not changed since the beginning of the world which reveals the fact that a man could not influence it. The main reason is that it is exclusively a product of the nature. However, the great changes influence both water (relation of drinking and salt water) and continental part of the planet. A man could not influence the changes caused by the natural factors. On the other side, a man is responsible for certain changes. Although the land is non-renewable natural resource the pressure on it was too huge in the previous century. This trend is popular in the XXI century, too.

2. GLOBAL PROBLEMS

From three billion in 1960 the number of inhabitants grew to 6,7 billion in 2009, and as of 2011 there are seven billion people living on the Earth. This number is constantly increasing, so by 2030 it could be expected to be 8,2 billion inhabitants, and by 2050 there will be near nine billion inhabitants (Graph.1).

Graphic 1. The increase of number of inhabitants from 1960 to 2009

Source: Republic Office of Statistics (RZS72010)

According to the data obtained from the UNCTAD in Serbia in 2012 the number of inhabitants dealing with agriculture amounted to 563.000 and participated in total labour force with 12,6 percent. With 355.000 of men there were total of 208.000 women dealing with the agriculture production. The number of men in this activity is higher by 70,7 percent.

In ancient year 1992 (corrected by estimated number in Montenegro) the number of those being in the agriculture was 1.218.000 and share of 27,7 percent in total labour force. With 630.000 of men there were 588.000 of women, so it means that there were by seven percent more men than women.

According to the projections for 2020 (when Serbia is expected to become the EU member-state) the number of people dealing with the agriculture will amount to 378.000, with the share of 8,3 percent in total employment rate. There will be 255.000 men, and 123.000 women and the number of men will be higher by 107 percent. As of 1992 the labour force in Serbia will increase by 3.3 percent by 2020. In that case, the number of those dealing with agriculture will be reduced by 69 percent.

This data on the trend in the labour force could be compared with the data referring to the countries being in transit, where a growth by 3,7 percent, while the data on the agricultural labour force might be compared with the developed countries where the decrease will amount to 70,6 percent. With the share of 12,6 percent of the agricultural in the total labour force in Serbia is 112.181 countries for which there are the data to be compared with the data for 2012. A higher share of the agricultural in the total labour force in Europe has only Albania (39,6 percent) and Poland (15,4 percent). Among the former Yugoslavian Republics the lowest share has Slovenia 0,6 percent, and only five countries have lower share such as: Qatar, Bahrain, Singapore, Brunei and the Netherlands Antilles. After Slovenia the lowest share has Bosnia and Herzegovina (2,5 percent), then Croatia (3,7 percent), while Macedonia (6,5 percent) has a half lower share of the agrarians in total labour force in Serbia.

Total area of the Earth is constant and amounts to 14,94 billion ha of agricultural or 2,22 ha. Such trend of growing number of inhabitants by 2050 will result in the reduction of total land from the current 2,22 to 1,66 ha, in other words, to 0,13 ha of arable land per capita.

Furthermore, since the beginning of industrialization, we witness taking of the arable areas for the construction of suburbs and business facilities. Therefore, the expansion of urban areas, industrial and technological parks, on one side, and constant increase of the number of inhabitants, on the other side, reduce not only total area, but the arable areas too, what is more important. In this way in the world near 30 million ha has been lost every year. For comparison, it is the size of whole Italy.¹

Industrialization is not the only problem. Cutting of forests, then turning of unfertile areas (meadows and pastures) into fertile and arable lands the problem of the lack of agricultural land is partly solved, but it endangers the ecological balance. At the same time, a dynamic growth of the number of inhabitants on the planet and a growth of the demand for food and purchasing power make the problem of rational use of the agricultural land more serious day in day out.

For example, in the world the arable areas increased by 1,8 billion ha in 2008 in comparison to 1992. This is the consequence of cutting forests and turning the meadows and pastures into arable areas. It happens, first and foremost in the countries of Asia, Africa, Latin America where a growth population is high. This is the reason why the arable areas are reduced from 0,28 ha (in 1992) to 0,22 ha (in 2010) per capita, which means that in the world the increase in population is more dynamic than the expansion of arable areas.

Although we have in consideration the figures aforesaid, we are mistaken that total agricultural areas in Serbia amount to near five million hectare and that the arable areas make up 4,2 million hectare. It is said that an average 0,56 ha is per capita, which is far more than in the Netherlands, Germany, which is our wealth, as someone states. In reality, we do not have these areas anymore. Because of the road construction and illegal construction on best arable areas and the fond of arable areas is getting reduced every year. The precise data do not exist, it is estimated that Serbia losses near 25.000 ha annually. On the other side, near 600.000 ha is not cultivated, which does not allow even more developed countries that Serbia is.

¹ Sundquist B., (2000) *Topsoil Loss – Causes, Effects, and Implications: A Global Perspective*, No.7, Revue - University of Minnesota

Table 1. Arable and non-arable areas (in 000 hectare)

1992	World	Europe	Serbia
Arable areas	1.512.302	318.791	4.076
Non-arable areas	11.547.557	1.941.103	6.124
Total:	13.059.859	2.259.894	10.200

2008	World	Europe	Serbia
Arable areas	3.440.708	303.993	4.225
Non-arable areas	11.526.172	1.956.106	6.476
Total:	13.066.880	2.260.099	10.200

(2008) FAO for the years listed

Observed at the global level the less arable areas per capita for the last four years have the countries showed in the *Table 2*

Table 2. Arable areas per capita²

Country	ha arable areas per capita (2006-2010)
United Arab Emirates	0,00
Japan	0,01
China	0,10
United Kingdom	0,10
The Netherlands	0,10
Mexico	0,20
France	0,30
Brazil	0,30
Serbia	0,40
Bulgaria	0,40

(2008) FAO for the years listed

When it comes to the countries with the developed market economy, first and foremost, on the territory of the European Union and transoceanic countries the problem concerning the reduction of arable areas solve in two ways. Firstly, they take care of the natural resources keeping under control the increase of inhabitants, and the second way is directly, through the environmental protection and particularly the public care of agricultural and arable areas. It is arranged by laws, regulations and directives. It is great importance because the interests of producers (whose motive is to make a higher profit), the consumers whose interest is better and cheaper food and the government of the national states and a group of states whose interest is to take care of the resources are being entwined and harmonized here. On the other side, the states with dense population (china, India) are forced to have two harvests annually, wider areas covered by irrigation system and higher usage of chemicals so as to provide healthy food for numerous populations, which makes the pressure on resources previously aforesaid.

3. NEAR 25 PERCENT OF GLOBAL AREAS DESTROYED

One forth of the global areas has been substantially destroyed and this trend must be changed so as to provide enough food for the whole inhabitants living on the planet constantly increasing are the results of the first UN survey on the condition of the global land and water resources.

² www.fao.org

The report discloses that 25 percent of the global land is currently destroyed at great extent, since there are the erosion of the soil, the reduction of water resources and the loss of biodiversity. Yet eight percent is 'slightly destroyed', while 36 percent is stable or slightly endangered, while only 10 percent of the land is improved. The rest of the world land is covered with deserts or water areas. The Western part of Europe is particularly endangered where the intensive agricultural production caused the contamination of the soil and underground waters and resulted in the loss of biodiversity, then Himalaya, Andes, Ethiopian Highlands and South Africa where there are the erosion and intensive floods. In the South-eastern and Eastern Asia the rise fields are deserted mostly due to the drop of the value of this agricultural produce. The UN Food and Agriculture (FAO) estimates that the agrarians will have to produce 70 percent more by 2050 so as to meet the needs of the world population which is expected to reach to nine billion people. It means that it will have to be produced one billion ton more of wheat, rice and other crops and 200 million ton more of beef and other kinds of meat. The current situation is such that the most fertile areas have already been cultivated but in a way to reduce their productivity and the soil is being exhausted and water spent. In order to meet the needs for food at the global level it is necessary to intensify the agricultural production on the already existing arable areas, the FAO estimates in the report titled 'The situation of the global land and water resources for food and agriculture'. The UN study reveals that the climate changes, together with bad agricultural practices, contribute to the reduction of productivity on the global arable areas at the time of big application of new technologies, pesticides and hybrids, which an instantly but shortly brought the increase in the crop yields. Thanks to new technologies in the agriculture only 12 percent more of the global land is sown with the crops in the period from 1961 to 2009, but the food production climbed by 150 percent. Meanwhile, the UN report shows, a growth rate in many sectors has been fallen down and today amounts to only a half of the mentioned figure. The UN report also indicates the global water resources are becoming decreased and more salty, while the underground waters are becoming more polluted with pesticides and other kinds of poison. To meet the needs for water at the global level by 2050 it is necessary to have more efficient irrigation systems, because the current ones are under their capacity, the FAO estimates.

This organization calls for the usage of new agricultural practices and higher investments in the development of agriculture. The UN considers that by 2050 it is necessary to invest 1.000 billion dollars in the development of irrigation systems in the developing countries, and yet 160 billion dollars for the recovery of the ground and the control of floods.

4. PROBLEMS WITH LAND UTILIZATION IN SERBIA

The problems with the land utilization on the global level were previously discussed. However, we have to act locally. First and foremost, we are interested in solving the problems with the utilization of arable land. Serbia officially has 5,11 million ha of agricultural and 4,22 million ha of arable land.³

Briefly, we will familiar you with five biggest problems:

1. Extensive utilization of land with extensive sowing structure and reduction of number of livestock;
2. A small number of private households (with an average three ha), which is significant obstacle for agrarians to become more bigger the goods producers;
3. reduced introduction of organic substances and lower level of usage of organic fertilizers, particularly of the muckheap;
4. Degradation of the land. Today in Serbia water and wind mostly cause the erosion which destroys the arable areas;
5. The lack of the irrigation systems

³ Data obtained from Republican Office for Statistics for 2008

1. Extensive production: In addition to the sciences and skills of the businessmen it could be said that in the last few decades the change of the structure towards functional and profitable intensive production has not happened. In the sowing structure there are still dominant grains (77 percent), and insufficient quantities of industrial crops, vegetables and fodder (23 percent). Intensive production makes higher profit per unit of area. Truly, it requires more capital and work, but at the same time it provides higher profitability. Apart from that the areas with vineyards are getting reduced and the existing vineyards are too old, with unequal sorts, low yield, bad quality and insufficiently profitable – which also indicator of the extension of production.

In the last two decades the number of the livestock in Serbia fell by three to four percent annually, and the meat production recorded a drop from 600.000 to 457.000 tonne.⁴ The worst situation has been recorded with the breeding stock, and in the beginning of this year the number of cows and in-calf cows is less by 28 percent in relation to 1991, and of sows and pregnant sows by even 60,8 percent. The data showed in the *Table 3* indicate the changes happened in the livestock breeding in the period 2009 - 2010.

Table 3. Change of number of livestock in Serbia between 2009 and 2010. ¹

Livestock	2009	2010	Change in %
Beef	999.406	935.444	-6,4
Pigs	4.064.628	3.922.366	-3,9
Sheep	1.521.140	1.492.239	-1,9
Poultry	22.786.399	20.120.391	-11,7

Long – term observation, particularly in comparison to the period 1988 – 1990 the number of beef is lower by 20,2 percent, pigs by 22,5 percent, sheep by 26 percent and poultry by 22,7 percent. In the extensive production the mineral fertilizers are insufficiently used. For instance, in the SFRY 120 kilograms of mineral fertilizers was used per hectare and then we were among the last one in the world. This consumption of mineral fertilizers is constantly falling down and today it reached 40 kilograms per hectare and according to this we are on the last position in Europe. It is the same situation with the irrigation system. In the world total of 17 percent of arable areas has been irrigated. In Serbia officially only 1,2 percent. There are irrigation systems on 70.000 hectares, while water comes to only 38.000 hectares.

This is the reason why we have low yields of all crops. For instance, in 1990 we had 4,38 ton of wheat per hectare, and in 2010 this number was between 3,2 and 3,5 tons, a year after that 4,2 tons, and in 2012 it was 3,9 tons per hectare. The wheat growing could not be profitable is the yield are below four tons per hectare.

4.1. Small households

Small households are the main obstacle for higher productivity in the commodity production and competitiveness. We are among the European countries with the smallest households. An average household is 3,3 hectare of arable land, and 2,6 hectare of plough fields. The reasons are in the traditional agricultural structure, non-arranged inheritance right, insufficiently created land policy. For instance, In European Union in 1957 an average size of household amounted to 4,8 hectares. In 2004, thanks to the measures of agricultural policy for the increase of household, its average size amounted to 44 hectare, in France 78 hectares, Denmark 50 hectares (Babović J. 2005). There are certain positive trends recorded in Serbia too, for example, an household of an average size 10-15 hectares has from 2,5 percent of share in 1991, in the structure of total areas, increased to near six percent in 2010. The enlargement of land is impossible without the performance of market mechanisms and planned long-term measures of the state, in other words, without their harmonized performance. It should be concern of the local self-governments, the related ministries, the associations and producers. Briefly, no enlargement of households, no rational production.

⁴ Data obtained from Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Serbia 2011

4.2. Reduction of content of organic substance

Organic substance plays an important role in the sustainability of tiny-crumble-like structure of land, the improvement of its chemical, biological, mechanical and physical features, being very important for the development of root system and successful plant growing. However, as it is already aforesaid, in the last few decades the number of livestock has been dramatically reduced and thus the production of stable manure. According to the official data the number of all categories of livestock has been decreased, not only in comparison with the 1980's, but with the last five years.

Dramatic reduction of the number of livestock for five years now resulted in negative effects on the development of agriculture and the economy of the Republic of Serbia on the whole as well as on the fertility of the land. The production of stable manure is reduced, which is important organic fertilizer whose role is to better fertility and wealth of the land. In addition to this, other kinds of organic fertilizers such as compost, green fertilizers are not used anymore.

There are yet another dramatic examples: in the last ten years the number of beefs in Serbia has been reduced by million or by 50 percent, pigs by million or by 20 percent, sheep by 1,1 million or by 40 percent and poultry by eight million or by 42 percent. The reduction of the number of livestock indicates that there is no need to enlarge the areas covered with fodder crops, also important crop improving fertility of the land, in particular, the growing of leguminosae plants. Upon terrible drought which took away 50 percent of the total yield in 2012, the slaughtering of livestock has been continued due to the shortage of fodder feed. The first estimates of drought damages are beyond two billion dollars, which is the sum enough for the construction of irrigation systems. The share of the livestock in the GDP used to be low only 30,5 percent, and now it is expected to be reduced to 25 percent. In the world this number is over 60 percent!

4.3 Degradation processes

These processes are caused by nature and a man. Those caused by nature are floods, underwater, erosion, winds drought. The erosion caused by water and wind are very dominant in the global agriculture. According to Stanimir Kostadinov (2000) the Total of the Serbian territory 86,4 percent is subject to erosion. The erosion causes the loss of fertile land, humus and it deteriorates its characteristics. The water and wind take away down to the rivers, seas and oceans the huge quantities of fertile soil. An annual level of the soil eroded is the highest in China (1.600 million ton), then in India (1.455 million ton), Brasil and Peru (1.363 million ton respectively), in the USA (300 million ton), Myanmar (299 million ton), Ethiopia and Egypt, Sudan (111 million ton respectively).

Taking into consideration strong degradation land processes in our country it is planned to forest near 50.000 hectare by 2010 (long-term 100.000 hectare) as well as to sow grass on near 80.000 plough fields lying on higher incline (Gulan B. 2000). However, it stayed an unfulfilled wish.

5. SHORTAGE OF IRRIGATION SYSTEMS

In Serbia only 1,2 percent of the agricultural land has been irrigated, while in the world near 17 percent of arable areas. In 1947 in Vojvodina the construction of the hydro system Danube – Tisa – Danube was commenced, then the largest investment in the SFRY worth 700 million dollars. It was officially finished and started to function in 1977. The system had double purpose: to drain too much water and to supply water during the drought. The aim of this system was to drain too much quantities of water from one million hectare area and to provide the water for irrigation of 500.000 hectares. Unfortunately, none of these aims are being met today. Namely, the irrigation of half a million hectares has never been realised, while the aim to drain too much water from one million hectares area was met by 2003. Upon too big floods either this activity was not any more in the function. According to some estimates this system contains near 12 million cube meters of mud (it needs to be revitalized, in other words, cleaned and made ready for drain of too much quantities of water). The situation is alarming when it comes to the channel network. Namely, the irrigation system has never been in function, while the drainage system used to work by a decade ago. Therefore, If we

take into consideration that Vojvodina has 22.000 kilometres under the channel network, we could irrigate near 44.000 hectares. I do not believe that it could be easily done, but a progress in that field could be made.

The data of the Republic Office of Statistics show that in Serbia in 2010 the area of total 27.246 hectares has been irrigated, while the total arable land in the country amount to near 4,2 million hectares. Therefore, in Serbia the larger areas in Serbia has been irrigated, than the statistics show, because it does not involve the irrigation in green houses. The areas irrigated in green houses amount to between 15.000 and 20.000 hectares, which means that in the country total of 40.000 and 50.000 hectares of agricultural land has been irrigated. There is a problem in Serbia concerning the neglected irrigation systems, which is the reason why water does not come to the areas needing the irrigation, indicating that the existing irrigation systems in Vojvodina could irrigate 100.000 hectares, and in Central Serbia near 60.000 hectares. In the former SFRY there were conditions for the irrigation of 180.000 hectares, and a certain part of these channels and hydro systems in Serbia are weeded. Water is a good servant, but evil lord is the slogan popular up to date.

It is important to enlarge the areas in the country requiring the irrigation, due to the scientific analysis which disclosed that in Serbia 51 year is dry in one century, and due to the bigger production of food. No irrigation, no intensive agricultural production, and no competitiveness both on the domestic and global market. The drought caused damage in one year only, as it was the case three year ago, is higher than the total investments in the irrigation systems. In order to solve this problem Serbia will have to adopt the strategy for development of agriculture and then to pass the long-term plan for fighting the drought and the rational program of irrigation of arable areas if it wants to keep the position of important producer and exporter of food. The analysis carried out by the World Meteorological Organization indicates that an average temperature at the global level will increase by two degrees this year, and for the last three years Serbia has had extremely high temperature in the summer periods. It has to be take into mind that in the last 100 years on the territory of Serbia each second year was dry, which is yet another evidence for solving the problem with irrigation. The irrigation could be better if the individual producers would be granted the cheap loans and without the interest rates, which would simplified the supply of the irrigation equipment, whether it is about the water aggregates or the drop-by-drop system. Therefore, the future dry period could be come over easily if the new sorts of plants would be created which will need less water for the same quantity of yields and would be more resistant to the extremely dry period. In addition to the creation of new sorts, as the most important task of the domestic agricultural experts appears the research works with a view to define best suitable irrigation system to varied types of lands and crops in the different parts of Serbia. It is the time to revive the visionary projects dating back to the 19th century concerning the construction of the way Danube – Vardar – Aegean sea and in this way to solve with the irrigation in the Central and Southeast part of Serbia. In the future it should be thought about supplying the water for the irrigation of Šumadija, through the construction of the channel Sava - Velika Morava - Zapadna Morava. It is mentioned the construction of the channel Danube-Morava-Vardar, which will be the biggest strategic project of the state, because Serbia should not allow others to take control over its natural resources.

For instance, in April 2011 the channel network in Banat was cleaned. In the normal conditions the cleaning of the channel network should not be done in April, but in December or January, in other words, when it is not the agricultural season. In February the snow is melting throughout Europe and the river levels are getting higher. This is the reason why the channel network should be cleaned in time so as the agricultural activities would be carried out in March, April and May. In addition, once in a year or two it is necessary to subvert the soil and break the so-called plough sole which is caused due to the mechanisation and which prevents the drain of water from the fields (Tomić D. and associates, 1996). The opinion is that there are intensive processes of souring, salting and pounding of land, along with the heavy metals.

The agricultural policy directed towards the development of agricultural production and fostering of the natural resources of Serbia should be the essential priority in overall development programme of Serbia both in the economic and social and ecological aspect. The negative trends in the agricultural production are showed through an growth rate of net agricultural production which in the last decade amounted to an average 1,3 percent, and its gross value was 1,9 percent, which are lower values if compared with the same period in the 1980's. An optimal growth model counted with an average growth rate of agriculture of 3,5 - 4

percent in the following ten years. Having in mind the structure of the agricultural production in Serbia, the resources and the level of productivity reached it is estimated that the changes will have to happen in the directions to the growth of productivity, stabilization of yield and the change of the production structure in the crop production and higher livestock breeding share in the value of the agricultural production. In order to achieve all these objects we must take care and use in a better way the existing land potential of Serbia.

It is necessary to finish the registry of the agricultural land for solving the issue of denationalization and restitution as well as for the creation of the pretext for new credit lines for buying the land. Therefore, the application of the agricultural policy which must involve the part saying the ways for keeping the current land potentials, in particular the attention must be focused on the equal regional development, the credit lines granting, the non-refundable assets for the improvement of production, the environment, the stimulation of the sale of domestic products on new markets, the development of new technology, the strengthening of competitiveness of the domestic production, the harmonization of new laws with the EU regulations, the constant increase of agricultural budget and the maximum level of subsidies. When adopting the measures in the agricultural policy it is necessary to have in mind that none of the countries made its prosperity without the development of agriculture. It is the case with Serbia too. The success and progress in the process of economic reforms in the field of agriculture depends on a growth of productivity, the increase of agricultural production and these are the key factors in the improvement of dynamic development of agricultural sector of the countries in transition. The main thing is how the land potential, which we borrowed from the future generations, of one country is used and protected.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Taking into consideration the aforesaid facts, the following conclusions could be made:

1. Land is non-renewable natural resource needed to the future generations, and thus it must be the issue of the public policy
2. The most favourable relation of the arable areas per capita have the transatlantic states, while the most unfavourable has the Asian countries. In the European countries and Serbia this relation is still satisfying.
3. A constant growth of the population on the planet and increased demand for agricultural produce intensified the agricultural production in the last century. It will happen in the future, too.
4. When it comes to the use of the land in Serbia, there are the problems as follows: extensive production, small households, insufficient use of organic substance and degradation processes caused by the nature and a mankind
5. On the long-term bases, the solutions for the crisis in the livestock breeding in Serbia are in the regulation of financing, return to the domestic and international market and the creation of strategic solutions which would stop the negative trends in the livestock
6. Global solution to the problem is in the more intensive use of land, the enlargement of households, increased use of organic substance and the reduction of degradation processes
7. With respect to all climate changes, frequent droughts, on one side, and available water resources, on the other, Serbia should substantially increase the areas being irrigated in the years to come.

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